

School Booklets for Secondary Education

6.4

Deliverable 6.4
August 2025

Executive Summary

Deliverable 6.4. School booklet on Contested Territories brings together a set of teaching materials intended for circulation in educational settings and among groups interested in working on the debates promoted by Contested Territories. **These teaching materials are directly linked to the generation of knowledge and experiences developed within the network** and include different methodological approaches that were also systematized by the Contested Territories teams.

The deliverable includes three areas of work:

6.4.1.- Urban Markets and Food Circuits. - Pag. 3

6.4.2.- Access to Housing: Commodification and Struggles for the Right to the City - Pag 23

6.4.3.- Disputes over Water- Pag 48

The first addresses the issues related to the basic right to food and the networks established for the production, distribution, circulation and consumption of food. In particular, it delves into the topic of urban markets, distinguishing between traditional and popular markets, markets affected by gentrification and touristification, and markets linked to agroecological circuits that promote healthy and nutritious food.

The second section develops issues and problems related to people's right to access adequate housing. It delves into the growing process of 'tenantisation' in European and Latin American cities, in both formal and informal neighbourhoods. It also addresses renewed forms of struggle and resistance, as well as actions to defend nature and common goods in cities. Ultimately, it is about conceiving the city as a space for living and enjoying collective rights.

The third axis refers to issues associated with territorial disputes over water as a central element for human life, agricultural production and other economic activities. It reviews the different meanings that water has for different cultures, eras and contexts. It argues that the issue of water cannot be approached from a single perspective and proposes an interdisciplinary approach to understand it in its multiple dimensions.

Each of these areas includes: a general introduction to the topic, key concepts, guiding questions, the cases addressed by Contested Territories research, and, finally, work proposals and methodologies in action. The proposals are organised around four dimensions and actions that challenge young people to take on a critical and active role: Explore, Interpret, Testimony and Take Action.

These activities include the use and production of a wide range of resources, such as maps, texts, images, audiovisuals, or the use of the Voces-Territorios platform, also generated within the scope of Contested Territories. Together, the suggested activities invite reflection and action, collaborative work and the development of collective projects, and the articulation of teaching and learning processes in an enriching dialogue with communities and territories. Young people are the protagonists of these proposals, which aim to move towards the construction of other futures that are socially more equitable and environmentally more sustainable.

ERIA DE ALIMENTACION

IDAD Y PRECIOS EN SU TIENDA AMIGA:

PESCADOS Y MARISCOS
ULTRAMARINOS
MAMONERIA Y SALCHICHERIA
REPARACION CALZADOS
POLLERIAS
CARNICERIAS
CHACINERIA

CASQUERIA
FRUTAS Y VERDURAS
VARIANTES
DROGUERIAS
FLORISTERIA
COMESTIBLES
PANADERIA

BAR
CONGELADOS
FRUTOS SECOS
REPARACION JOYAS
AFILADO
REP. PA
CD's Y OS

Urban markets and food circuits

School Booklet

6.4.1

Deliverable 6.4
August 2025

Authors of this booklet

Jorge Blanco | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
Editor | Argentina

Luciana Bosoer | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
| Argentina

Beatriz Estévez Cedeño | Universidad de La Laguna, Tenerife
| España

Itahisa Pérez Pérez | Universidad de La Laguna, Tenerife
| España

Pedagogical advisor

Raquel Gurevich | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
| Argentina

This publication is the result of a collective writing experience. The authors are especially grateful to Miguel Kanai for his review and to Alejandro Armas-Díaz, Héctor Grad, Patricia Urquieta, Romina Olejarczyk, and the participants in the Encuesta Inquilina project for their comments and observations.

Graphic design

Alberto Nanclares da Vega | Basurama - Madrid, Spain

Cover photo: Two elderly at the doorstep of a food market in the process of transformation into a supermarket
Ciudad Lineal, Madrid, Spain. Photography: Elvira Megías, 2021

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Deliverable 6.4.1:

School Booklet

Urban markets and food circuits

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Knowledge and learning in action

We invite you to explore and use this material from the Contested Territories network. Our aim is **deepening the readings and experiences that the network has been carrying out in contact with various communities** that collaboratively build, negotiate, imagine and manage their territories in power relations that are always unequal and in constantly contested.

Through this proposal and the treatment of certain topics, we hope to **help you better understand your own territorial experiences, take action and participate** in collective situations aimed at improving the living conditions of diverse communities.

We offer you and the teaching and coordination teams that accompany you a **set of concepts and analytical tools, but above all proposals for interpreting and inventing scenarios that go beyond the existing ones.**

The idea is to multiply encounters with various actors/agents in the community, in your schools and other social settings familiar to you, to produce conceptual and empirical knowledge about territorial inequalities, opening up new questions, perspectives and paths to resolution.

PLEASE NOTE

It is YOU, the youth, who are the main characters for this proposal, which does not stop at analysing and explaining the situations studied, but aims to move towards the construction of alternative, inclusive proposals that bring together multiple disciplines and knowledge.

Contested Territories proposes interventions to build other futures that are socially more just and environmentally more sustainable. We are counting on you to help make these goals a reality and enrich them with your creative and contextualised contributions.

Three school booklets

This proposal consists of three materials **organised around the following content areas:**

Urban markets and food circuits

Access to housing: commodification and struggles for the right to the city

Disputes over water

The first addresses the issues **related to the basic right to food and the networks established for the production, distribution, circulation and consumption of food.** In particular, it explores the issue of urban markets, distinguishing between traditional and popular markets, markets undergoing gentrification and touristification, and markets linked to agroecological circuits that promote healthy and nutritious food.

The second module develops **topics and issues related to people's right to access decent housing.** It delves into the growing process of "tenantisation" in European and Latin American cities, in both formal and informal neighbourhoods. It also addresses renewed forms of struggle and resistance, as well as actions to defend nature and common goods in cities. Ultimately, it is about conceiving the city as a space for living and enjoying collective rights.

The third axis refers to issues **associated with water conflicts and disputes as a central element for human life, agricultural production and other economic activities.** We review the different meanings that water has for different cultures, times and contexts. We argue that the issue of water cannot be approached from a single perspective and propose an interdisciplinary approach to understand it in its multiple dimensions.

Each of the materials consists of fixed sections, where you will find an **introduction to the topic, key concepts, guiding questions, case studies** from Latin America and Europe, **as well as a proposal for work and specific methodologies for researching, writing and intervening in your areas of action.**

Introduction

The United Nations recognises **food as an essential part of people's individual and social lives.**

It is so important that it **considers access to food on a regular, permanent and unrestricted basis to be a universal human right.**

Access to food can be achieved through self-production or purchase, but it must always be adequate and sufficient in terms of quantity, quality and cultural consumption patterns. In other words, the right to food guarantees the development of a satisfactory, dignified and fear-free physical and mental life, both individually and collectively.

Along with the recognition of this basic right to food, there is a need to consider **the networks that are established in its production, distribution, circulation and consumption.**

At Contested Territories, we understand that these complex networks are linked to processes of territorial disputes and closely linked to social and geographical inequalities.

The processes of **globalisation, commodification and neoliberalisation** are intertwined with popular resistance and alternative models that emerge in this circuit, creating tensions across rural and urban areas.

Territorial tensions and conflicts arise around issues such as access to food, food quality, distance from the place of origin, and the socio-technical processes involved in production.

In this way, the territories involved in food production can be thought of as nodes and flows, in a relational way, in which social actors and places are linked in a network of circulation of people, goods, emotions, meanings and power.

Introduction

This is why it is important to pay attention to **the origin of food**, whether it comes from short, local circuits or long circuits; **the techniques** used for production, preservation and transport; and the **social organisation** of production, for example in the form of businesses or small producer groups. In this approach to the subject, other terms may arise that help us interpret the various situations that arise in these food networks, **such as agroecology, global production or marketing chains, cooperativism, different types of markets, fair trade and food sovereignty.**

Recognising the **diversity of workers** involved in food production and distribution is a very important aspect. It is labour that adds value to products and is expressed at different times and under varying conditions in which workers carry out their activities: from the field where work is intended for primary production to the industries where food is processed.

We also consider **the transport** that makes the circulation of production possible and **the markets**, of different types and sizes, which include small and large shops and restaurants, as well as distributors who deliver fast food through the streets, among others.

These diverse work scenarios linked to the food production circuit reflect the different social relations that are put into action by the chains of production, marketing and consumption, involving multiple actors, from the family, community and cooperative levels to global production and marketing in supermarket chains.

We can also consider how these food networks unfold in different territorial contexts: **in rural areas of different types, in peri-urban areas, in commercial areas of cities, in markets or on the streets themselves.** Other forms that we also include are street fairs and markets. In fairs, which are open spaces, both marketing and product exchange relationships take place. There are also producer cooperatives that sell directly to consumers in enclosed spaces, open spaces or on the street, and informal street trade fairs through trade fairs.

In each of these contexts, **disputes also arise**, for example, over the use of resources such as water and land, the advance of urbanisation into food production areas, the location of businesses, and pressure to transform neighbourhood markets that are embedded in certain parts of the urban fabric.

Introduction

In this proposal, we are interested in focusing our attention on urban markets.

We refer to markets as places where buyers and sellers meet, where a set of social relationships are established through exchange and through networks of food production, circulation and consumption. In this case, markets are a constituent element of the urban environment and have traditionally been associated with the commercial function of cities. From a material point of view, there are different types of markets. One example is buildings that were specially constructed or adapted to house sellers and welcome buyers, known as traditional markets. But a broader view also includes meeting places that are set up periodically for this purpose, such as fairs and street markets.

In the case of markets, we are interested in looking at different types of public policies and tensions that arise in the face of urban transformation processes, such as the gentrification of neighbourhoods and the tendency of markets to offer products specifically aimed at tourists to the detriment of the needs of popular or traditional consumers in the neighbourhood (touristification; gourmetisation of markets).

We will focus on the resistance of various social actors to some of these processes and on the alternative proposals generated by different social groups through collective organisation strategies.

With regard to food quality, **discussions are framed by new forms of consumption, concerns about production technologies and interest in healthy and nutritious food, the inclusion of food in care tasks, etc.**

These consumer cultures are closely linked to forms of production, for example, through an interest in fresh food produced without agrochemicals and from seeds that have not been genetically modified.

Both production and distribution and consumption patterns have environmental implications in terms of land and water use, the application of techniques that make production sustainable in the long term, the management of production and consumption waste, the type of packaging used to market products, the type of vehicles used for transport, energy consumption and emissions generated.

Key concepts

Traditional urban markets

Historically, cities have always been linked to commercial activity. Although there is no single type of market, traditional markets date back to the 18th, 19th and early 20th centuries and emerged as an initiative of local governments to regulate trade and accompany population growth.

Most of them are located in the oldest parts of cities and are housed in covered buildings that were expressly designed and built for the sale and storage of various types of products. They also have all the necessary services and facilities, such as loading and unloading areas, circulation areas, toilets, warehouses, parking, security, etc. Currently, we are seeing traditional markets undergo a series of transformations associated with new patterns of production and consumption imposed in the neoliberal context, or they are emerging as spaces of protest and resistance, offering alternative food networks and circuits.

Agroecology

Unlike the hegemonic models of food production based on the artificialisation and standardisation of food, agroecology presents an alternative and sustainable approach. Agroecological practices are concerned with the environmental processes that take place throughout the food production cycle and are presented as a form of resistance to the processes of food commodification. Agroecology seeks to maintain short production circuits that do not pursue the industrialisation of food but rather consider access to and quality of food and the rights of producers.

Key concepts

Fair Trade

This is a commercial exchange relationship based on dialogue, transparency and respect, which seeks greater equity in international trade. It contributes to sustainable development by offering better trading conditions and ensuring the rights of small producers and the most vulnerable workers. Fair Trade Organisations, supported by consumers, are actively engaged in supporting producers, raising awareness and developing campaigns to bring about changes in the rules and practices of conventional international trade. The principles of Fair Trade include, among other conditions, the payment of a fair price, the absence of child labour and forced labour, non-discrimination and respect for the environment (UN, ECLAC, 2024).

Food production circuits

This refers to the entire path that food takes from its origin to final consumption. These circuits are made up of different stages that are integrated with each other, which is why they are also known as links in the same chain. In the case of food, the sequence consists of production, processing, distribution, marketing and final consumption. In addition, this circuit involves various social actors with different interests and strategies for action, from small producers or family farmers to large global production or marketing chains. When there is a certain proximity between the food producer and the consumer, this is referred to as a short circuit; conversely, when there are many links and several intermediaries involved, it is a long circuit.

Cooperativism

This is the name given to the movement that brings together different types of cooperative experiences. We understand a cooperative to be "an autonomous association of persons united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise" (International Cooperative Alliance, 1995). In many cases, collective organisation functions as a strategy of contestation and resistance, through alternative practices generally based on agroecological production and fair trade.

Key concepts

Gender equality

Thinking about gender equality in relation to food invites us to consider the role that people play throughout the food system. Traditionally, domestic, food and care tasks have fallen to women, which we know as unpaid work. But there are also differences in paid work, in the distribution of domestic tasks, in the wage gap and in access to the labour market between men and women. Women and other gender identities face historical, social and structural disadvantages. A gender equality approach seeks to redress these inequalities with measures, standards or policies that respond to the real needs of each person, according to their historical and contextual conditions.

Invisible or unpaid work

This is work that is performed without any payment. It mainly includes domestic work and caring for children, the elderly, people with disabilities and/or sick people. This unpaid work is mainly performed by women and contributes to both family and national economic development. The lack of economic quantification makes the role played by women invisible at the macroeconomic level, generating a negative impact on their autonomy and economic empowerment, while also preventing the presentation of quantitative evidence for the formulation of public policies and support for those who perform these tasks (UN Women, 2015) (PAHO, 2008).

Guiding questions

These questions guide the reading of the material and aim to provide an overall understanding of this proposal.

They are not meant to be answered at this point, but rather to raise questions that will accompany us throughout this experience.

¿How can we guarantee the universal right to sustainable and safe food?

What do we know about the quality of what we eat?

How and where is the food we consume produced?

What role have women historically played in food production and preparation?

What social actors and processes come into play with regard to the food available for consumption?

Selected case studies

To address this broad spectrum of issues, we will use various case studies from the **Contested Territories network**, in cities such as **Leeds (United Kingdom)**, **Madrid (Spain)**, **Berlin (Germany)** and **Buenos Aires (Argentina)**. **FIND THEM AT:**

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Booklet-de-acumulacion-territorial_compressed.pdf

(Leeds, Buenos Aires and Madrid)

Popular markets, food consumption and production circuits

In **Leeds, UK**, it is possible to understand the significance of markets at different points in history and the effects of the current supremacy of supermarket chains.

In **Buenos Aires**, we will explore some alternative models of production, distribution and consumption.

(Madrid, Spain)

Markets and neighbourhoods against gentrification

En Madrid hay una amplia variedad de situaciones que van desde los mercados tradicionales o alternativos hasta aquellos sometidos a fuertes procesos de turistificación y gentrificación.

(Berlin, Germany)

Organic supermarkets. "BIO" food in Berlin

In **Berlin** we will hear the voices of producers and consumers of organic products and learn about the emergence of organic supermarkets.

In addition to that experience, the following visual materials are available to complement the information and experiences on new forms of food production and distribution:

<https://www.contested-territories.net/trilogia-biomercados/>

"BIO" food in Berlin. "ECO" food in Madrid. "AGRO" food in Bs As

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Explore

Welcome to the Territorial Accumulation Atlas on the Contested Territories website.

At first glance, take a look at the tabs and labels on the page. As you will see, there are multiple ways to present the information: by country, on a general map, by case.

Discover...

What is the purpose of the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation?

What topics are covered?

Are some topics or cases addressed more than others?

Are all countries included?

How is the information displayed?

What tools are used?

We suggest you review the information by going to the general map shown in the Atlas <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/mapa-general/> and consult the **reference table**.

Which of the cases presented are related to food, markets and food production?

Which cases and countries did you find?

If you look again at the reference table,

which cartographic tools are used?

Organise the information in a table so that you can share your results collectively.

The Atlas also allows us to access cases based on the country of our choice

<https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/por-pais/>

Check if, **based on this new entry**, there is any new information or new resources that allow you to learn more about the topic being presented.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Explore

We also invite you to explore the "Voces-Territorios" platform, which is a participatory tool for making geolocated information visible and sharing it in various formats (such as photographs, audio, videos), building a collaborative map of the dynamics, interventions and conflicts in the territory.

<https://www.vocesterritorios.com/map>

You can enter the Collective Map section and explore the dimensions in which the information is organised, for example, sociocultural processes, emotions, etc.

Would you like to add any situations or interventions related to urban markets and food circuits?

Which ones?

To do so, you must consult the app's requirements before downloading it and creating a user profile. In it, you can describe the situation or intervention and adapt it to the five dimensions proposed: territorial processes, sociocultural processes, emotions, types of struggle, types of action.

Which of these caught your attention the most?

Why?

Which of these refer to processes related to the topic of food that were discussed in the previous table?

If necessary, add a column to the table to include this new information.

- Procesos Territoriales
T

¿Qué pasa con el territorio?
- Procesos SocioCulturales
S

¿Cómo afecta a las culturas?
- Emociones
E

¿Qué sentimientos se reflejan?
- Tipos de Lucha
L

¿Qué lucha concreta se refleja?
- Tipo de Acción
A

¿Cómo responde la comunidad?

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Interpret

Each of the cases we have selected

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Booklet-de-acumulacion-territorial_compressed.pdf

contains keywords at the beginning of their presentations.

**Make a list of the keywords from the cases.
What do they have in common?**

CASE STUDIES	Popular markets, food consumption and production circuits	Markets and neighbourhoods against gentrification in Madrid	Organic supermarkets. "BIO" food in Berlin
KEY WORDS			

Read the cases carefully and use different colours to identify and select the phrases that refer to:

Local or alternative commercial circuit

Commodification of food production circuits

Touristification

Popular markets

Gentrification

Agroecology

Fair trade and cooperativism

Food quality

Right to food

Public regulations

Alternative models of food distribution and access

Based on what you have learned so far, discuss in groups:

What economic and political conditions impact the development of gentrification processes in contemporary cities? What relationships do you find between popular markets and possible gentrification processes?

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Interpret

 What elements stand out as benefits or potential in the processes of change in popular markets?

**Good accessibility
in terms of transport**

**Location in
central areas**

**Nearby
consumer market**

**Commercial
infrastructure**

**Symbolic and
cultural value**

 Please apply the following tags to the photos that you think best represent the processes studied

<http://contested-cities.net/CCmadrid/tres-mercados-en-una-ciudad/>

Keep the following aspects in mind:

How are the goods arranged or presented for sale? In what language or languages are the signs written? Who do you think the products are intended for? What products are being offered? Where do you think they come from? Are they ready for immediate consumption? Or are they used to produce other foods? What are the characteristics of the sellers and consumers? Do you think they are neighbours of the market or just passing by?

Local shops

Catering and
gourmet food outlets

Popular markets, identities and neighbourhoods

Cooperative strategies

Fresh produce

Agroecological products

Products marketed
by and for migrant groups

Gourmet products

Gentrified and
tourist-oriented markets

Food production and consumption
in the neoliberal city

Urban markets as sites
of dispute and resistance

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Interpret

 We suggest you check out the following publication, which compiles a series of podcasts.

<https://www.contested-territories.net/podcast-otras-maneras-de-investigar>

There is no podcast on the topic of "Markets, touristification and gentrification". Would you like to create one?

We recommend visiting the following link to learn more about narrative research through conversational podcasts.

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/CT_DELIVERABLE2.2-JUNE2024.pdf

First, you must select the case you want to work on. It can be one from your locality or another where you can gather information through different sources and resources. These methodological decisions will be explained in the podcast.

Don't forget that the section is called "Other ways to investigate," so feel free to create new ways to access information and contact the protagonists of the case. It is important to give space to women's own stories, for example, peasant women, farmers, community cooks, food entrepreneurs, or food sovereignty activists.

The first task is to write the conceptual script, then listen to it and edit it until it becomes an audio script, add music and schedule the sounds you want to add.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Testimony

We invite you to make an experimental video based on testimonials and/or first-person accounts about “bio”markets, farmer’s markets or alternative markets

To begin, watch the videos "Lo bio en Berlín" (“BIO” food in Berlin), “Lo ECO en Madrid" (“Eco” food in Madrid), and "Lo agro en Buenos Aires" (“Agro” food in Buenos Aires).

<https://www.contested-territories.net/trilogia-biome mercados/>

What are the main themes presented in these videos?

Who are the people giving their testimonials?

What role do they play in the food system? What advantages and obstacles arise for this type of production?

Does it exist or is it viable in the community where you live?

Why?

- Once you have decided on a topic, write down the questions you will ask and think about who you would invite to share their experiences. You can ask members of your own family (think about who is responsible for shopping, who makes the shopping list, who decides what to eat and who prepares meals in your home; perhaps it is the same person or perhaps these tasks are shared). You can also interview people you have chosen in advance (those who sell food in shops or on the street, people who work in restaurants or who shop at markets) and people you meet spontaneously in your neighbourhood.

- Once you have the testimonials, we suggest that you spend a week drawing or describing how food is organised in your homes. Then, share the results in groups and analyse whether there are gender patterns.

- Do you find equality? Investigate the difference between gender equality and gender equity.

-Write a short text summarising the main contributions obtained from the testimonies.

Now you are ready to put together the video, with your tags, appliqués, music, and a relevant title.

Access to housing: commodification and struggles for the right to the city

School Booklet

6.4.2

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Authors of this booklet

- Jorge Blanco | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
Editor Argentina
- Paula Lanusse | Equipo Antropología, Ciudad y Naturaleza - Área de estudios urbanos, Universidad de Buenos Aires
Argentina
- Vanina Lekerman | Equipo Antropología, Ciudad y Naturaleza - Área de estudios urbanos, Universidad de Buenos Aires
Argentina
- Marina Wertheimer | Equipo Antropología, Ciudad y Naturaleza - Área de estudios urbanos, Universidad de Buenos Aires
Argentina
- Luciana Bosoer | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
Argentina
- Beatriz Estévez Cedeño | Universidad de La Laguna, Tenerife
España
- Itahisa Pérez Pérez | Universidad de La Laguna, Tenerife
España

Pedagogical advisor

- Raquel Gurevich | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
Argentina

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Deliverable 6.4.2:

School Booklet

Access to housing: comodification and struggles for the right to the city

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The third axis refers to issues **associated with water conflicts and disputes as a central element for human life, agricultural production and other economic activities.** We review the different meanings that water has for different cultures, times and contexts. We argue that the issue of water cannot be approached from a single perspective and propose an interdisciplinary approach to understand it in its multiple dimensions.

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Introduction

Housing is a right enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The constitutions of almost all countries also recognise **the right of people to access decent housing**: that is, with adequate space, basic services and good infrastructure, under legal conditions that ensure tenure.

The recognition of housing as a right implies that States, at the national and/or subnational level, have an obligation to establish the necessary measures to prevent possible violations of this right, especially among the most vulnerable.

We know, however, that **a significant part of the population suffers from various types of housing problems.**

These difficulties affect both people living in cities and those living in rural and peri-urban areas. In this proposal, we focus on cases studied by the Contested Territories network in the cities of Buenos Aires (Argentina), Santiago (Chile), Madrid, Barcelona and Tenerife (Spain), as well as Lisbon (Portugal).

In these cities, as in many others around the world, changes have taken place over the last two decades that have increasingly limited access to decent housing. For this reason, the Contested Territories network maintains that housing has become a central issue in understanding the suffering of people today, and that there is an urgent need to reverse trends that have exacerbated inequalities and various conflicts.

The right to adequate housing includes access to urban common goods such as proximity to transport, schools, hospitals, workplaces, government offices, outdoor recreational spaces, and living in areas without environmental risks.

This leads to another right linked to housing: **the right to the city**, a set of principles that urban social organisations have been promoting for years. The right to the city is a collective right, defined by UN-Habitat as the right of all people to inhabit, produce and transform cities, towns and urban settlements in a fair, inclusive, safe, sustainable and democratic manner. The right to the city also involves protecting biodiversity, natural habitats and ecosystems in the surrounding environment.

Introducción

Demanding the fulfilment of the right to housing – ensuring adequate environmental conditions and the right to the city – is becoming an urgent task, especially when we consider how our cities are growing.

Some experts have called '**neoliberal urbanism**' the way cities are developed, which prioritises attracting investment over meeting social needs and caring for the environment. As a result, many services and common goods have been privatised and commodified.

While living conditions worsen for large sectors of the population, parts of the city become restrictive for the majority and are used to satisfy the consumption and luxury housing needs of the wealthiest sectors. To analyse these processes, the Contested Territories network contributes the idea of territorial accumulation, which explains how the expansion of capitalism is not limited to the economic sphere, but also manifests itself geographically, transforming territories through dynamics of extraction, control and conflict.

In Latin America, processes of territorial accumulation acquired an extractivist characteristic.

This term was initially used to describe processes of territorial dispossession linked to large-scale mining projects, hydrocarbon exploitation, or the advance of agribusiness. More recently, however, the concept of **urban extractivism has become** popular among social organisations and in academic circles.

This concept seeks to denounce the aggressive way in which economic gains generated in the primary productive system have been channeled into cities, especially in the real estate sector. Given the instability of the banking system, so-called 'investment in bricks and mortar' has also become a safe way for middle-class savers to protect the value of their capital. Investments are made in the renovation of buildings, the construction of new buildings, shopping centres and gated communities, with the aim of ensuring that the commercial operations derived from the ownership of these properties provide returns similar to those of the financial market. The concentration of real estate supply in the hands of these investment groups significantly increased the value of housing, with the consent of local governments, which often allowed these projects to be carried out by providing land or other types of state resources.

Introducción

Similar processes can be observed in central countries, where there is a large presence of new purely financial actors in the real estate market. Banks, "vulture funds," technological platforms such as Airbnb, developers, real estate investors, and rentiers of all levels are hoarding homes and turning them into financial assets.

This process is called the **financialisation of housing**. From this perspective, housing is no longer understood as a basic right or a vital need, but is instead conceived primarily as a means of making money and doing business. In these systems, housing is often integrated into large international markets where it is bought and sold as if it were bonds or shares on the financial market. This logic creates uncertainty and instability for those who live in these homes: their right to remain there is not guaranteed. At any moment, they can be sold or rent prices can increase, and their inhabitants can face eviction or displacement.

An important consequence of all these structural transformations in real estate markets and urban policies is that there are fewer and fewer homeowners and more people renting housing on the private market.

Tenancy is a growing process in European and Latin American cities, in both formal and informal neighbourhoods. The possibility of accessing home ownership has been eroded for various reasons: rising prices and stagnant wages, lack of mortgage credit, and the absence of public policies that prioritise the social function of housing. Accessing housing through private rental is no longer a temporary condition or one specific to young people who are leaving home, but rather a permanent reality for increasingly large sections of the adult population.

At the same time as the number of tenant households has grown, conditions for accessing rental housing have deteriorated significantly due to phenomena such as the financialisation of housing, gentrification, touristification, the explosion of temporary rentals, rising prices and the growth of informality. This process not only delays the emancipation of young people, but also has a particularly severe impact on households supported by women, single-parent households, households where people with disabilities live, among the working classes and migrant groups. In short, what has been lost is the right to a stable space where people can build a home in fair and dignified conditions. The situation is so critical that more and more people are living in precarious conditions and are being forced onto the streets. Although tenantisation is a growing phenomenon, there is very little official data on how difficult and discriminatory access to housing has become. For this reason, the Contested Territories network has joined forces to implement a tenant survey in different cities, which will help to raise awareness of the problem and show how it has affected people's quality of life.

Introducción

In response to this situation, **new forms of struggle for housing and the city have emerged in recent years.** These include diverse forms of resistance and proposals: occupations of vacant land and housing, riots against evictions and dispossessions, self-managed housing cooperatives, campaigns for alternative policies to control rents, municipal referendums to nationalise housing in the hands of "vulture funds", legislative projects to regulate tourism, tenants' unions and grassroots organisations against price increases and residential insecurity, among others.

There are also actions to defend nature and common goods in cities: social collectives opposing the privatisation of squares, parks, beaches and coastal areas, the creation of community gardens, the defence of woodlands, and the reforestation of public spaces to restore biodiversity. This wide range of forms of struggle shares a common goal: to reclaim the city as a space for living and enjoying collective rights, in the face of relentless commodification and individualisation promoted by neoliberal capitalism

In this material, you will find, on the one hand, the results of the tenant survey carried out by the Contested Territories network in the cities of Barcelona, Madrid, Lisbon and Buenos Aires. The survey is a tool whose use continues to expand, as it proved to be very powerful in revealing both the particularities of the tenantisation processes in each city and the numerous elements they have in common.

On the other hand, it addresses cases related to two rental submarkets: short-term or temporary rentals and room rentals. It analyses how temporary rental technology platforms in Buenos Aires and Santiago de Chile have concentrated the supply of rental housing. It also studies how difficulties in renting have driven a sector of the middle class in Buenos Aires towards renting or subletting rooms, displacing popular sectors that historically made use of this modality. Another case, located in a neighbourhood in the historic centre of Lisbon, will allow for a more in-depth analysis of the impacts of touristification on the housing market and the community fabric, as well as the strategies developed to resist these transformations. Finally, cases from the island of Tenerife and the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area will help to understand the violation of the right to the city in a broad and comprehensive sense, which includes environmental resources and the use of nature.

We invite you to read the cases studied by the Contested Territories network using the conceptual tools presented, and to think of others that you consider necessary. We particularly recommend paying attention to the forms of struggle and resistance that have emerged in different parts of the world to defend the right to housing and contest meanings of the city, taking into account who holds the right to the city and the ways of inhabiting it.

Key concepts

Territorial accumulation

The term refers to the processes of appropriation and control of space to extract value, displacing communities and reconfiguring territories under capitalist logic. Territorial accumulation responds to processes such as the commodification of land, the privatisation of public assets and corporate governance, and highlights how capital transforms spaces into financial assets, prioritising profits over rights and sustainability. This is the case, for example, in Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain), where the local government intends to declare a protected area of La Tejita beach as suitable for urbanisation in order to develop and expand tourism. Activists and local residents are fighting to protect the landscape, ecosystem and natural and cultural heritage, debating development models and their effects.

Urban extractivism

The notion of urban extractivism began to be used in recent years in Latin America to reflect on the dynamics of dispossession taking place in cities. According to this concept, cities absorb surplus capital which, in the face of banking instability, is poured into the real estate sector. The resulting products (housing, shopping centres, gated communities) function as financial assets with rates of return similar to those of other markets and, as a result, land and property prices rise significantly. These processes exclude large sections of the urban population, degrading their living conditions and giving rise to new conflicts and territorial tensions. In cities such as Buenos Aires, for example, the construction of new housing has grown significantly in the last two decades as a way of investing "in bricks" to protect savings and generate profits. This real estate boom contrasts, however, with a worrying reality: at the same time, the number of home-owning households has declined. More and more people are excluded from access to home ownership due to high costs, forcing them to turn to the rental market. This dynamic deepens inequalities and contributes to the phenomenon of tenantisation that we analyse here.

Key concepts

Financialisation of housing

The financialisation of housing is the process by which housing is transformed into a financial asset, prioritising its exchange value over its social function. It involves the growing influence of banks, vulture funds, technology platforms such as Airbnb, developers, investors and rentiers at all levels of the real estate market, generating speculation, price increases and exclusion. This phenomenon deepens urban inequalities, displaces communities and consolidates neoliberal logic in access to housing. In cities such as Lisbon, for example, at the end of the 2000s, in a context of economic recession, the local government launched an urban regeneration agenda as an anti-crisis strategy aimed at attracting tourism and international investment. Urban construction requirements were simplified and municipal properties were put up for sale, without any public policies to guarantee local residents access to housing. As a result, the city is now experiencing a profound housing crisis that particularly affects women, gender and sexual minorities, migrants and the working classes. To learn more about this issue, please consult the tenant survey and the case study on the Mouraria neighbourhood in Lisbon.

Tenantisation

The concept of tenantisation refers to the socio-economic process in which the population dependent on renting to access housing grows massively as a result of the commodification of land and the financialisation of real estate. According to studies by the Contested Territories network, this phenomenon is driven by neoliberal urban policies that favour investors over residents. It leads to greater housing insecurity due, among other things, to high rents, abusive contracts, instability, covert evictions (e.g. through rent increases) and the risk of forced displacement. It particularly affects vulnerable groups, accentuating urban inequalities and transforming the basic right to housing into a speculative commodity controlled by powerful actors, investment funds and large capital holders. This is a growing phenomenon in Europe and Latin America, in both formal and informal neighbourhoods. To better understand its impact on people's lives and on the urban social landscape, we recommend reviewing the results of the tenant survey conducted in Madrid, Barcelona, Lisbon and Buenos Aires. In the latter city, the survey also specifically analysed how the growing tenantisation affected the submarket for room rentals. Middle-class sectors, excluded from the formal rental market by rising prices and contract requirements, began to occupy rooms in hotels, guesthouses and tenements, displacing lower-income sectors that now face more critical housing situations.

Key concepts

Struggles for housing

The notion of struggles for housing encompasses collective resistance to land accumulation, which seeks to defend access to housing as a social right and not as a commodity. This idea includes a wide range of actions such as mobilisations, occupations and political demands against evictions, abusive rents and real estate speculation. These struggles, led by social movements and affected communities, challenge the neoliberal urban model and propose alternatives such as cooperatives, legal occupations and redistributive public policies, demanding the right to the city and to housing, the social function of land and decent housing. Trade unions and tenants' associations, for example, have been gaining prominence in recent years in cities such as Madrid, Barcelona, Lisbon and Buenos Aires. These organisations have grown as conditions for access to secure rental housing have worsened, and they tend to bring together very diverse social sectors, united in the struggle for access to decent housing and the right to the city.

Gender equality

In terms of housing, gender equality means understanding that not everyone starts from the same position when it comes to exercising their right to the city. Women and other gender identities face historical, social and structural disadvantages. A gender equality approach seeks to redress these inequalities with measures, standards or policies that respond to the real needs of each person, according to their historical and contextual conditions.

With regard to housing, it is not simply a matter of distributing resources such as loans or subsidies for purchase or rent equally or universally. Factors such as the gender pay gap, access to the labour market and the extra burden of care work must also be taken into account. In cities such as Buenos Aires, the results of the tenant survey showed that the situation of precariousness, housing instability and vulnerability is significantly worse in households headed by women, especially when there are children and/or persons with disabilities.

Guiding questions

These questions guide the reading of the material and will help you formulate your answers as you carry out the proposed activities.

By the end of the course, you will be able to understand and explain your position on each of the issues raised in greater depth.

How can we guarantee the universal right to housing in cities?

How can we make our cities more equitable places?

Why has access to housing become increasingly difficult?

Why do women face additional difficulties in accessing decent housing, especially when they are sole carers?

Which actors and processes dominate decisions about how cities are produced?

Selected case studies

To analyse tenantisation processes and their effects:
tenant survey in Buenos Aires, Lisbon, Barcelona and Madrid.

(Lisboa, Buenos Aires y Madrid)

The tenant's odyssey

Details about how the tenant surveys were made, their global objectives and comparative objectives.

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Booklet-acumulacion-2_compressed-1.pdf
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Tenant survey report in Greater Buenos Aires, Argentina

acij.org.ar/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Encuesta-inquilina-AMBA-1.pdf

Tenant survey report in Barcelona, Spain

<https://idrabcn.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/estudio-generacion-inquilina-WEB-CAST.pdf>

Tenant survey report in Greater Lisbon, Portugal

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/informe-lisboa_10-04-25_castellano.pdf

Comparative reports Madrid - Barcelona

<https://idrabcn.com/es/publicacion/>

Selected case studies

To analyse the **short-term rental submarket:**

(Buenos Aires, Santiago de Chile)

Impacts of technology platforms on the rental market in Santiago, Chile, and Buenos Aires, Argentina.

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Booklet-acumulacion-2_compressed-1.pdf

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To analyse the **room rental submarket:**

(Buenos Aires)

Impacts of tenantisation processes on room rentals in Buenos Aires, Argentina

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Booklet-acumulacion-2_compressed-1.pdf

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Selected case studies

To analyse processes of territorial accumulation and violation of the right to the city in a comprehensive sense: urban expansion, privatisation and commodification of coastal and green spaces in Tenerife and the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area.

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Booklet-acumulacion-2_compressed-1.pdf

(Tenerife)

Fighting for the right to the island in La Tejita, Tenerife, Spain

(Buenos Aires)

Popular habitat vs. gated communities. Contradictions and conflicts in the southern periphery of AMBA, Arg.

(Buenos Aires)

Environmentalisation of conflicts and social policies in disputed territories in the AMBA, Argentina

Selected case studies

To analyse forms of struggle for housing:

(Buenos Aires, Santiago de Chile)

How were the tenant surveys actually made?

Alliance between academia, tenants' unions and other social organisations for the design and implementation of the tenant survey within the framework of the Contested Territories project

<https://www.contested-territories.net/como-se-han-hecho-las-encuestas-inquilinas/>

(Lisboa)

Mouraria, Lisbon: from tourist gentrification to articulating urban change

Struggles against touristification and gentrification in the Mouraria neighbourhood of Lisbon.

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Booklet-acumulacion-2_compressed-1.pdf

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Work proposals and methodologies in action

Explore

Welcome to the Territorial Accumulation Atlas on the Contested Territories website.

At first glance, take a look at the tabs and labels on the page. As you will see, there are multiple ways to present the information: by country, on a general map, by case.

Discover...

What is the purpose of the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation?

What topics are covered?

Are some topics or cases addressed more than others?

Are all countries included?

How is the information displayed?

What tools are used?

We suggest you review the information by going to the general map shown in the Atlas

<https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/mapa-general/> and consult the **reference table**.

Which of the cases presented are related to urban extractivism, access to land and housing, and tenantisation processes?

Which cases and countries did you find?

If you look again at the reference table, **which cartographic tools are used?**

Organise the information in a table so that you can share your results collectively.

The Atlas also allows us to access cases based on the country of our choice

<https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/por-pais/>

Check if, **based on this new entry**, there is any new information or new resources that allow you to learn more about the topic being presented.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Explore

We also invite you to explore the "Voces-Territorios" platform, which is a participatory tool for making geolocated information visible and sharing it in various formats (such as photographs, audio, videos), building a collaborative map of the dynamics, interventions and conflicts in the territory.

<https://www.vocesterritorios.com/map>

You can enter the Collective Map section and explore the dimensions in which the information is organised, for example, sociocultural processes, emotions, etc.

Would you like to add any situations or interventions related to housing struggles and the right to the city

Which ones?

To do so, you must consult the app's requirements before downloading it and creating a user profile. In it, you can describe the situation or intervention and adapt it to the five dimensions proposed: territorial processes, sociocultural processes, emotions, types of struggle, types of action.

Which of these caught your attention the most?

Why?

Which of these refer to processes related to the topic of housing that were discussed in the previous table?

If necessary, add a column to the table to include this new information.

Procesos Territoriales

T

¿Qué pasa con el territorio?

Procesos SocioCulturales

S

¿Cómo afecta a las culturas?

Emociones

E

¿Qué sentimientos se reflejan?

Tipos de Lucha

L

¿Qué lucha concreta se refleja?

Tipo de Acción

A

¿Cómo responde la comunidad?

Work proposals and methodologies in action

Interpret

Each of the selected cases found on the pages 14-17

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Booklet-de-acumulacion-territorial_compressed.pdf

contains keywords at the beginning of the presentation.

 Make a list of the keywords from the case studies. What do they have in common?

	KEY WORDS
<i>The tenant's odyssey</i>	
Short term rentals in BsAs and Santiago	
Room rental market in Buenos Aires, Arg	
Mouraria, Lisboa, Portugal	
La Tejita, Tenerife, Spain	
Environmentalization of conflicts and social policies in BsAs, Argentina	
Popular habitat vs. gated communities	

 Organise yourselves into groups and read the selected cases. Using different colours, identify and select the phrases that refer to:

- Urban extractivism**
- Right to housing**
- Right to the city**
- Tenantisation**
- Gender equality**
- Rental submarket**
- Gentrification**
- Financialisation**
- Environmentalisation of public policies**
- Touristification**

 Based on what you have learned so far, discuss in groups:
 What economic and political conditions impact the development of urban extractivism in contemporary cities? What relationships do you find between access to the city, housing, and the possible processes of tenantisation, touristification, and financialisation that are taking place?

Work proposals and methodologies in action

Interpret

 The following list shows different aspects of neighbourhoods in touristified or gentrified cities:

**Transport
accessibility**

**Location in central
and/or tourist areas**

**Commercial
infrastructure**

**Tourist and
consumer areas**

**Symbolic and
cultural value**

**Gender
perspective**

**Select one of the cases we have been studying
(Lisbon, Buenos Aires, Madrid, Barcelona, Tenerife)**

look for images, photographs, posters or tourist information that illustrate these aspects. Add a brief explanatory caption to each image or document you collect.

Don't forget to cite the source of each of the materials consulted.

 In working groups, identify local organisations in your city or municipality that are involved in the struggle for decent housing, against evictions, touristification and gentrification, and in defence of green areas, among others.

- **What is the profile of the groups that make up these organisations?** Are they women, men, non-binary people? Where do they work (public sector, private sector, independently, formally or informally)? What is their level of education (basic or primary, secondary, university or other)? Are they native or migrant? What social classes do they belong to? What other characteristics can be considered to describe the members of these organisations?
- **How are these groups organised?** What kind of actions do they propose? Are there leaders? Is it a grassroots organisation?
- **Which residents do you consider to be most vulnerable?** What additional obstacles do they face?

Work proposals and methodologies in action

Interpret

 Now we suggest you take a closer look at how the housing market data was constructed in the cases studied.

Access the videos and images at the following links to learn about the different methodologies used and their particularities.

<https://www.contested-territories.net/como-se-han-hecho-las-encuestas-inquilinas/>

<https://www.contested-territories.net/ficcion-inmobiliaria-en-la-boca/>

<https://ciudadesreveladas.com.ar/la-odisea-inquilina-en-el-amba/>

You can focus on some of these aspects and then discuss them together:

- What research methodologies are used to analyse tenantisation processes in different cities?
- What does it mean to conduct a survey?
- What significant indicators from the tenant survey would you highlight?
- How can the phenomenon of tenantisation in recent years be explained and how does it relate to the right to housing?
- Are there any questions that would allow us to reconstruct the gender perspective in terms of access to rental housing?
- What does it mean to adopt a militant methodology?

 In working groups, research the press (local news, municipal or national reports, NGOs, interviews with experts, etc.) on the housing situation of women in your region.

You can focus on cases of evictions, women in informal settlements, access to subsidies or housing programmes, etc.

Investigate:

- Which concepts covered so far can be related to and explain the new cases studied?
- Make a list of the main needs that are exposed in the new case.
- Identify the actors and their roles in the proposed actions and decision-making.

Work proposals and methodologies in action

Testimony

We tend to think of testimonies as oral accounts, words and stories recovered from first-person protagonists about a certain event or process.

On this occasion, we invite you to explore a new form of testimony: visual testimony.

On the website of the Museum of the Displaced (Museo de los Desplazados) <https://www.lefthandrotation.com/museodelosdesplazados/colaboraciones/memorias-de-lisboa/> you will find the photographic project "Memories of Lisbon: Jojo's Struggle", by Manu Huertas. Through images, it documents the urban transformations of Lisbon due to rampant tourism and gentrification. It also makes us think about the loss of traditional professions through the eyes of Jojo, a boot cleaner who has been working in this trade for decades.

 We invite you to create a textual version of this visual testimony. You will have to translate the visual language into a written narrative.

The museum's website tells us that "Jojo is one of the last two tenants in a building in the city centre, whose modest livelihood as a boot cleaner is under threat due to the arrival of a foreign investment fund that plans to convert the building into tourist flats". What would Jojo say if we asked him about the situation he is experiencing, what his days are like, what worries him, what he plans to do? To write the text, first write down your impressions of the images, paying attention to Jojo's face, the particular objects that appear, the details of the street, the lighting and anything else that catches your eye when you look at the photos.

One more piece of information you can add to the text: the museum's presentation states that "Memories of Lisbon: Jojo's Struggle is a visual testimony to the struggle for survival and resistance of a city facing the threat of losing its soul."

Once you have finished your testimonies, share your work and discuss the different versions that each of you has produced. There will undoubtedly be common and recurring aspects, while others will be completely new, different and unique.

Work proposals and methodologies in action

Testimony

 To focus on the issue of gender, we invite you to look for testimonies or life stories of women who are single mothers and have experienced housing problems (eviction, informal housing, violence, exclusion, etc.)

Analyse these stories, identifying the obstacles they faced, how they overcame them and what support they needed. Finally, define what structural changes would be necessary to improve the situation of these women.

Compare these stories with Jojo's case: what aspects are repeated and what are the particularities found?

 Based on the information you have gathered, we suggest you produce content to upload to the Voces-Territorios App

You should adapt it to the five dimensions proposed: territorial processes, sociocultural processes, emotions, types of struggle, types of action.

- Procesos Territoriales** T
¿Qué pasa con el territorio?
- Procesos SocioCulturales** S
¿Cómo afecta a las culturas?
- Emociones** E
¿Qué sentimientos se reflejan?
- Tipos de Lucha** L
¿Qué lucha concreta se refleja?
- Tipo de Acción** A
¿Cómo responde la comunidad?

Work proposals and methodologies in action

Take action

Are you familiar with the tool of montage film making?

It is a technique that combines different audiovisual products (films, videos, clips) and any other visual form of information and communication. It reuses existing material and regenerates it into a new discourse, giving it new meaning. In doing so, it gives the story a new direction, as in a collage, which can be critical, metaphorical, parodic, among other possibilities.

We suggest you take the theme of "The right to housing and access to shelter" and create a montage film about it.

First of all, **compile all the images, audiovisual productions and photographs that you have been viewing in this proposal**, plus any others you wish to add, into a file. Number each one so that it will be easier to find them later.

You should construct a story or script that articulates and organises the images in a coherent manner. If you wish, you can add an opening and closing with your own audio recordings, as the narrator group.

To get in the mood and start writing the script, you can draw inspiration from the name of Case 11, "The Tenant's Odyssey," remembering that the term odyssey refers to a long, difficult journey full of adventures and hardships. We recommend that you keep the following ideas in mind to give substance and rigour to the visual montage you are going to create:

- Living conditions of the tenant population
- Neoliberal urban models
- Role of the state
- Legislation/deregulation of the property market
- Organisational strategies of resistance

For more resources when creating your film montage, please consult the publication <https://www.contested-territories.net/toolkit-approaching-contested-territories/>

Finally, you can organise an event to present the visual product, which you can accompany with a short performance where you discuss what the montage is about, the pieces that make it up, the methodologies involved and how the material was developed.

Which organisations or individuals fighting for the right to housing and/or the city could you invite to the presentation?

Where would be a good place to show the work you have done to support these struggles?

Disputes over water

School Booklet

6.4.3

Deliverable 6.4
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Authors of this booklet

- Jorge Blanco | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
Editor | Argentina
- Carlos Salamanca | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
| Argentina
- Luciana Bosoer | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
| Argentina
- Beatriz Estevez Cedeño | Universidad de La Laguna, Tenerife
| España
- Itahisa Pérez Pérez | Universidad de La Laguna, Tenerife
| España

Pedagogical advisor

- Raquel Gurevich | Instituto de Geografía - Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires
| Argentina

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- Alberto Nanclares da Vega | Basurama - Madrid, Spain

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Deliverable 6.4.3:

School Booklet

Disputes over water

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Knowledge and learning in action

We invite you to explore and use this material from the Contested Territories network. Our aim is **deepening the readings and experiences that the network has been carrying out in contact with various communities** that collaboratively build, negotiate, imagine and manage their territories in power relations that are always unequal and in constantly contested.

Through this proposal and the treatment of certain topics, we hope to **help you better understand your own territorial experiences, take action and participate** in collective situations aimed at improving the living conditions of diverse communities.

We offer you and the teaching and coordination teams that accompany you a **set of concepts and analytical tools, but above all proposals for interpreting and inventing scenarios that go beyond the existing ones.**

The idea is to multiply encounters with various actors/agents in the community, in your schools and other social settings familiar to you, to produce conceptual and empirical knowledge about territorial inequalities, opening up new questions, perspectives and paths to resolution.

PLEASE NOTE

It is YOU, the youth, who are the main characters for this proposal, which does not stop at analysing and explaining the situations studied, but aims to move towards the construction of alternative, inclusive proposals that bring together multiple disciplines and knowledge.

Contested Territories proposes interventions to build other futures that are socially more just and environmentally more sustainable. We are counting on you to help make these goals a reality and enrich them with your creative and contextualised contributions.

Three school booklets

This proposal consists of three materials **organised around the following content areas:**

Urban markets and food circuits

Access to housing: commodification and struggles for the right to the city

Disputes over water

The first addresses the issues **related to the basic right to food and the networks established for the production, distribution, circulation and consumption of food.** In particular, it explores the issue of urban markets, distinguishing between traditional and popular markets, markets undergoing gentrification and touristification, and markets linked to agroecological circuits that promote healthy and nutritious food.

The second module develops **topics and issues related to people's right to access decent housing.** It delves into the growing process of "tenantisation" in European and Latin American cities, in both formal and informal neighbourhoods. It also addresses renewed forms of struggle and resistance, as well as actions to defend nature and common goods in cities. Ultimately, it is about conceiving the city as a space for living and enjoying collective rights.

The third axis refers to issues **associated with water conflicts and disputes as a central element for human life, agricultural production and other economic activities.** We review the different meanings that water has for different cultures, times and contexts. We argue that the issue of water cannot be approached from a single perspective and propose an interdisciplinary approach to understand it in its multiple dimensions.

Each of the materials consists of fixed sections, where you will find an **introduction to the topic, key concepts, guiding questions, case studies** from Latin America and Europe, **as well as a proposal for work and specific methodologies for researching, writing and intervening in your areas of action.**

Introduction

Water is social, but it is also environmental and belongs to the spheres of life, politics and the economy.

There are many reasons why water, with its **multiple natures**, has become a central terrain of current territorial tensions. Even if we think of the same territory, in the current times when the effects of global warming and climate change are most intense, water can mean scarcity and overabundance, depending on the time of year, the seasons and other environmental dynamics. It is a common paradox that communities that experience flooding are the same ones that face unmet water demand or lack access to quality water; these situations are referred to as water stress.

Water is central to human life and to agricultural and economic production, although in certain circumstances, the two seem to be at odds. The same lake or river that means life and even the basis of collective identity for farmers and Indigenous Peoples is often simply a landscape that can be translated into profitability and economic value for companies and States. For the former, defending water and territory is a matter of their very identity and collective life; for the latter, it is a matter of business and economic accumulation.

The environmental sustainability of territories depends on water, since certain ways of organising the territory or water flows can mean the prevention of disasters or the creation of risky situations.

In recent years, academic and artistic research practices have found in water a central axis for addressing, analysing and proposing perspectives on the complexity of the contemporary world.

What other element links realities, geographies, territories, interests and different social sectors like water does? Or environmental, social, political and economic issues? What other element is so dynamic, alive, changing and multifaceted?

It is now clear that water cannot be approached from a single perspective; therefore, an interdisciplinary approach is required to understand it in all its complexity.

Introducción

For reasons that we will describe below and that derive from the work experience of the Contested Territories network, current territorial disputes are often expressed in water, over water and through water. In the feature-length documentary "La Cuenca" (The Basin), filmed in southern Chile in 2023, for example, we can see how there are very different views, perspectives and expectations surrounding water. For some sectors of society, **water is a consumer good** or an attractive and decorative element of a landscape suitable for real estate projects. For others, **water is a living being with which they maintain a relationship of care**, reciprocity and affection. They even consider it a relative, as Luis Catrilef from the Mapuche people tells us. That is why Carlos Quiñenao, also from the Mapuche people, asks: Can water live? And if water can live, he affirms: "water can be killed." That is why it is possible to understand that "the people of the land" are "there to protect water."

Some also see water as a superabundant resource that can be used as a place to dump waste, sometimes without much awareness, sometimes with total pragmatism. As the documentary "La Cuenca" shows us, it is also used for economic purposes, as other sectors **use water as a tourist attraction**.

And all this happens at the same time.

If we consider these tensions and conflicts in a temporal sense, it is possible to see that their origins can be traced back years, decades or even centuries, and that the effects of these tensions can be projected into different time frames in the short, medium and long term. For example, the colonisation of indigenous territories in the border regions of Latin America, such as southern Chile, involved the radical and seemingly definitive denial of different ways of living with water, glaciers, rivers and the sea. This is also referred to in the expression of water as a relational element, a characteristic that has been taken up by environmental movements such as Aguas Libres Villarica, when they state: "We are all everything".

Based on the erasure of indigenous knowledge and philosophies and peasant communities by various states, a series of actions are being carried out in the territory that deny both their presence and the relational dimension of water, of which these peoples are an active part. This denial has multiple implications, one of which is violence. Celsa Isabel Saravia, from the Aguas Libres Villarrica movement, links something as small as a jug she found with a history of violence and usurpation that lies beneath, silenced.

Along the same lines, the growing levels of pollution caused by enterprises such as salmon farms in southern Chile will have a medium- and long-term impact on the entire lake, affecting the lives of humans and animals there. It can therefore be said that **territorial tensions involving water can be better understood in their multiple temporalities**.

Introducción

Water is relational.

This means that it connects the peaks of glaciers and snow-capped mountains with the lowlands or the sea. Water connects the commonality of shared environments, with water as a shared space, with the most intimate corners of life in domestic spaces. Indeed, water connects rivers with hundreds and thousands of toilets in Villarrica and Pucón in Chile, as in most towns and cities in Latin America, whose waste, through intricate pipes, is discharged into rivers and then into lakes or other communities. In this regard, we can also look at the cases of the Bolivian communities of Chiluyo and Lukurmata, whose inhabitants, affected by pollution, have even had to migrate. The forms of pollution can be diverse. The cases of Bolivian communities discussed here also include peri-urban communities such as those of Puchukollo, which are exposed to pollution from landfills and real estate development.

Just as water links salmon farms with tourist ventures, it also links property speculators with Indigenous Peoples. Water unites different sectors in conflicts that need to be resolved because conflicts are relationships. And these conflicts and relationships must be described, analysed and addressed in order to think about solutions. To this end, there are different types of tools that allow us to understand that the different actors involved in these conflicts do not compete on equal terms. They allow us to understand that **relationships with water are marked by inequality.**

The materials made available here show that states, with their regulations, infrastructure and even their armies and security forces, sometimes favour the interests of certain socio-economic groups to the detriment of others. For example, public policies that support business interests against the demands of indigenous peoples, peasants or small landowners.

The materials also show us that there are communities living surrounded by water without access to drinking water, shopping centres built on cemeteries and indigenous sacred sites, and communities such as Milluni, in the Katari basin in Bolivia, whose territories are contaminated by mining waste.

Slogans such as "water is worth more than gold" and "it's not drought, it's plundering" that constantly emerge in many corners of Latin America refer to this inequality and these struggles for water.

Introducción

Another case analysed by the interdisciplinary teams of Contested Territories is that of the Katari River Basin. The teams have produced videos, maps and texts that reveal the complexity of the relationships involved in a basin in situations of social, economic and environmental vulnerability. These alternative research tools are interrelated and, like a jigsaw puzzle, we can put the pieces together to better understand what a basin is.

Upstream and downstream, indigenous communities in vulnerable situations are fighting for their well-being, although sometimes thinking and acting separately. In the Katari Basin, which encompasses territories of nine Bolivian municipalities and accounts for almost 10% of the country's total population, the rubbish dumped into the Pallina River has an impact hundreds of kilometres away when it reaches Lake Titicaca. And this is just one example. Various types of solid and liquid waste are dumped into the rivers of the basin, affecting the communities along the basin to varying degrees, with serious situations such as that of the community of Cohana.

And here the knowledge of experts comes to the fore in the voice of Carlos Revilla, who asks us: How does a river 'enter' a city and how does it 'leave' it? What does it bring us and what does it take away?

Looking at the case of the Bolivian cities of El Alto, Viacha and Laja, Revilla insists on the need for "awareness-raising", "monitoring" and "control" measures. Do we know what these mean?

Water shows that everything is connected: pollution, scarcity and excess, the body and the territory, different economic activities overlap and generate territories in conflict. In these scenarios, the different tools invite us to ask ourselves: who are the actors involved? Which of them are present and which are absent? The fact that some actors are not very visible in the territory often has to do with a problem of scale, a term that comes from geography and refers to the area we consider when analysing a particular problem. States and multilateral organisations, among others, although they may not appear to be present, act in territorial conflicts involving water; this is why it is possible to say that **water is multi-scalar**.

Let us look at other dimensions. Bolivian leader Gregoria Paxipatty shows us how social, productive and economic histories accumulate on top of each other in the territory. Fishing involves a very different relationship with the lake than farming or herding animals. And when water dynamics change, production systems change, and with them, ways of life.

For all these reasons, we can say that water will become increasingly important in territorial conflicts in Latin America and the world in general.

You can find other perspectives on water in the "To watch and read" section on page 24 of this document.

Key concepts

Basin

A basin refers to a region or territory that encompasses all surface and groundwater that flows to the same point of exit, whether a river, lake or sea. It articulates both social and natural elements. The basin articulates high and low lands and the entire complex system of water bodies such as rivers, estuaries, lakes and streams.

Governance

Governance is the set of processes, institutions and actors—state and non-state—that are involved in decision-making and the management of collective resources. It involves a network of relationships in which international organisations, corporations, NGOs, local communities and the state itself interact. However, in Latin America in general, the discourse of governance has been co-opted by neoliberalism, serving to legitimise the withdrawal of the state in the name of 'participation' and 'efficiency', while opening the way for private actors to become involved in the management of public affairs.

Disputes over water

These reflect the tensions and conflicts that arise from the opposition between different social actors, communities, companies and others, as well as the way in which water is conceived and managed as a common good or as a commodity.

Guiding questions

These questions guide the reading of the material and will help you formulate your answers as you carry out the proposed activities.

By the end of the course, you will be able to understand and explain your position on each of the issues raised in greater depth.

Why is an interdisciplinary approach necessary to understand the multiple dimensions of the water issue?

How is the issue of water linked to territorial conflicts and tensions?

What meanings does water have for different cultures, times and contexts?

Why is water a central element for human life and all activities in general?

Selected case studies

We suggest working on the following cases and on the network's audiovisual production, **FIND THEM AT:**

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Booklet-de-acumulacion-territorial_compressed.pdf

Pag. 12

(Buenos Aires, Argentina)

The salado basin, Buenos Aires, Argentina.

To analyse water in its dimension as a resource and as territory

Pag. 20

(La Paz, Bolivia)

Infrastructures and logics of hydrological dispossession. Bolivia

To analyse water as a living space, as a commodity, in its historical context, as a resource, as territory and as a subject

Pag. 43

(Patagonia chilena)

The Mallolafquenh or Lago Villarrica basin, Chile

To analyse water as a commodity, in its historical context, as a resource, as territory and as a subject

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Explore

Welcome to the Territorial Accumulation Atlas on the Contested Territories website.

At first glance, take a look at the tabs and labels on the page. As you will see, there are multiple ways to present the information: by country, on a general map, by case.

Discover...

What is the purpose of the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation?

What topics are covered?

Are some topics or cases addressed more than others?

Are all countries included?

How is the information displayed?

What tools are used?

We suggest you review the information by going to the general map shown in the Atlas

<https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/mapa-general/> and consult the **reference table**.

Which of the cases presented are related to water disputes and territorial conflicts involving water?

Which cases and countries did you find?

If you look again at the reference table, **which cartographic tools are used?**

Organise the information in a table so that you can share your results collectively.

The Atlas also allows us to access cases based on the country of our choice

<https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/por-pais/>

Check if, **based on this new entry**, there is any new information or new resources that allow you to learn more about the topic being presented.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Activate the territory

The territory, the landscape, the city, the basin.

There are many ways in which we can think about the spaces we inhabit, get to know them, make them our own, scrutinise every corner, and understand them.

There are also many ways in which we can activate them, mobilise them, make them speak, listen to them, value them, and highlight them.

Cities, with their modernisation processes and their search for their own identity, have often distanced themselves from their past, their surroundings and, especially, their natural environment and their waters.

Rediscovering these silenced memories and forgotten pasts is a revealing action that can help us understand how the environments we inhabit work. To this end, rather than thinking about discovering a territory 'as it was', it is stimulating to ask ourselves how a landscape is and how we are with it, not only here and now, but in space and time in motion, as becoming.

Visible and invisible infrastructures and water flows

Schools can be thought of beyond the walls that limit them, and also beyond the present in which they are located.

Water is also interdependent on the water networks that feed it, which carry the water we use every day. At the same time, it needs water infrastructure to carry the water we dispose of in toilets or drains and grates.

To understand the concept of water metabolism, we can ask ourselves: where does water come from? Where does water go? We can think through examples that we all have a role to play in caring for water, but that we also have different degrees of responsibility.

We invite you to imagine or draw the paths that connect the school with its surroundings.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Activate the territory

Water stories. Exploring maps

There are numerous map repositories on the internet. Historical maps of our region, our city or our neighbourhood.

In Latin America, cities and towns were founded as part of a colonisation process, close to fertile soil and water sources such as rivers, lakes or streams. With the rapid modernisation of our cities, these water sources were often channelled, paved and covered.

Historical maps allow us to reconnect with the history of water and, therefore, with the presence of water in the history of our neighbourhood or city, in our own history.

We invite you to search the internet for historical maps of the area where you live and find the water sources, infrastructure and sanitation works, channelled rivers or streams, etc.

What differences do you find compared to the current situation?

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Activate the territory

Curated walk

Under the name of *performative territory*, the **collective Ciudades Reveladas (CR)** invites artists and all kinds of collectives to launch exercises that activate the city's centres and peripheries until they are reversed. In a series of jolts and upheavals that take place step by step, participants see how places that until then were indifferent, unknown or distant to them are awakened, rise up and come out to meet them.

"Butarque is the name of a stream" is one of these performance territories created in June 2025 in the city of Madrid as the result of a collaborative action between CR, Paisanaje and artist Malú Cayetano.

Under the name "curated walk", participants are invited to explore images, sounds and stories of what still murmurs beneath the asphalt of Madrid.

In an exercise in which attendees become detectives and explorers, the waters of Butarque emerge here and there, fresh, beautiful and in motion, dirty, foul-smelling and polluted, stagnant and putrid, pleasant and refreshing, visible and invisible. With them, the question also arises about the actors who make up these territories and these waters and the place that each one occupies and can occupy in this story.

We invite you to imagine and design walks, encounters and activities in the environment that allow participants to approach these surroundings that we sometimes do not see. To construct questions and actions that allow us to think about and understand these territories, their conflicts, their functioning and their poetics. To invite others to think and act. On these paths, water territories are particularly powerful because they unite what we think of as separate.

It is not just about walking. Discovering these watery cities with their rivers and streams also requires preparing the conditions for an encounter. Archives and libraries, the voices and memories of residents, photographs and videos. Prior research and collaboration to activate the territories and go out to meet them.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Interpret

Each one of the selected cases shown in pag 14 FIND THEM AT:
https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Booklet-de-acumulacion-territorial_compressed.pdf
 contains keywords at the beginning of its presentation

**Make a list of the keywords from the case studies.
 What do they have in common?**

CASE STUDIES	The Salado Basin. Argentina	Infrastructure and logic of hydrological dispossession, Bolivia	The Mollolafquenh or Villarrica Lake Basin. Chile
KEY WORDS			
Water, a relational element			
Water taken as a commodity			
Territorial tensions over water			
Water and its multiple temporalities			
Water, a living being			
Water and its multiple uses			
Water and inequality			

What are the prevailing views on how water should be conceived in each of the cases mentioned? Mark them in the table with a cross.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Interpret

 In the case of the Salado River Basin in Argentina, three perspectives converge: environmental, hydrological and productive. On the map of the province of Buenos Aires, each line (in red, blue and green) delimits an area that corresponds to each of the perspectives. Activate and deactivate these lines with the specific icon and discuss in groups which one corresponds to each of them.

<https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/la-Cuenca-del-salado/>

Which of these actors are linked to each map?

Educational and research institutions

Environmental organisations

Residents, neighbours, inhabitants

Agro-export companies

Producers and contractors

Agricultural cooperatives

Public institutions

Why is this considered a multifaceted and multiscale problem?

What scales of analysis are relevant for addressing disputes in the basin?

Think as a group about how the choice of scale influences the understanding of the territory in question.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Interpret

These three perspectives provide us with a complex understanding of the Salado Basin. We now invite you to indicate for each of the maps which element prevails in its definition.

Complete the table with the terms suggested below. You may also add others that you consider relevant:

	Economic Practice / activity	Actors involved	Natural conditions at play
Productive Focus / map			
Environmental Focus / Map			
Hydrological Focus / Map			

Fertile soils

Grasslands

Wildlife (birds, reptiles)

Rivers and streams

Lagoons

Watercourse rectification

Precipitación

Siembra directa

Use of agricultural technology

Sustainable livestock farming

Intensive livestock farming

Humedales

Native flora

Groundwater

Environmental education

Environmental conservation

Hydraulic works

Climate conditions

To finish, explain in your own words what you understand by the following phrase: "**One basin, several realities**".

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Interpret

 The case of the Katari River Basin in Bolivia refers to a set of urban and rural problems. What similarities and differences do you find between this case and that of the Salado River in Argentina?

 Please check <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/bolivia/> and page 20 of the document: https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Booklet-de-acumulacion-territorial_compressed.pdf write a ten-line note commenting on the actors involved and **reflect on the role they play** in relation to hydrological dispossession in the Katari Basin (Bolivia). **Consider gender relations. Do you think they are fair and equal? Are these fair or unfair relationships changing or remaining the same over time? Are they becoming more acute?**

 Based upon the film Uma Uñjirinaka (Cuidadores del agua) <https://vimeo.com/1072988301> make a list of the environmental issues mentioned. **Which of the images** shown in the video caught your attention the most? **Why?**

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Explore

We also invite you to explore the "Voces-Territorios" platform, which is a participatory tool for making geolocated information visible and sharing it in various formats (such as photographs, audio, videos), building a collaborative map of the dynamics, interventions and conflicts in the territory.

<https://www.vocesterritorios.com/map>

You can enter the Collective Map section and explore the dimensions in which the information is organised, for example, sociocultural processes, emotions, etc.

Would you like to add any situations or interventions related to water disputes and conflicts?

Which ones?

To do so, you must consult the app's requirements before downloading it and creating a user profile. In it, you can describe the situation or intervention and adapt it to the five dimensions proposed: territorial processes, sociocultural processes, emotions, types of struggle, types of action.

Which of these caught your attention the most?

Why?

Which of these refer to processes related to the topic of housing that were discussed in the previous table?

If necessary, add a column to the table to include this new information.

- Procesos Territoriales** T

¿Qué pasa con el territorio?
- Procesos SocioCulturales** S

¿Cómo afecta a las culturas?
- Emociones** E

¿Qué sentimientos se reflejan?
- Tipos de Lucha** L

¿Qué lucha concreta se refleja?
- Tipo de Acción** A

¿Cómo responde la comunidad?

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Testimony

In the case of the Mallolafquenh Basin or Lake Villarrica, what are the three main problems?

Are these isolated problems or are they related? Briefly describe each of them and explain why the documentary film "La Cuenca" states that "the basin is a whole."

<https://www.contested-territories.net/la-Cuenca/>

The documentary film "La Cuenca" made by the collective Left Hand Rotation presents powerful images and is based on a series of very significant testimonies about the issues addressed.

Which of the testimonies impressed you the most? Why?

In the first two minutes of the documentary and in the final minute, only images are shown and sounds of nature are heard; there are no stories or human voices.

If you had to include your testimony after seeing and hearing these scenes, **what would you say?** How did what you saw make you feel? How did the images and sounds in the video affect you?

You can rehearse your testimonies first and then refine your stories until you feel they are clear and rich enough.

What would you include in the first few minutes?

What would you include in the final minute?

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Take action

 We propose that you develop a collective documentary script on "Water Disputes."

There are many ways to accomplish this task. For example, you can consult **the following productions by the Left Hand Rotation collective, which will provide you with creative and original ideas.**

**"UMA UÑJIRINAKA
(Cuidadores del Agua)"**

<https://vimeo.com/1072988301>

**"Tigre es Yaguareté"
(Tiger means yaguareté)**

<https://vimeo.com/1029599880>

Are you familiar with the tool of montage film making?

It is a technique that combines different audiovisual products (films, videos, clips) and any other visual form of information and communication. It reuses existing material and regenerates it into a new discourse, giving it new meaning. In doing so, it gives the story a new direction, as in a collage, which can be critical, metaphorical, parodic, among other possibilities.

On this occasion, we recommend using the elements of the Tool Kit (point 9).

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/CT_DELIVERABLE2.2-JUNE2024.pdf

First, consult what this practice consists of, which is based on the "exquisite corpse" technique. **What is its usefulness and why is it said to be a political object?**

As a first task, and following the methodology suggested in the Tool Kit, each member of the collective script should choose two words.

Then, they should link the selected words together in a chain. We suggest that you write down the contributions so that you can rewrite and adjust the narrative thread as necessary. Keep in mind that this is a circular story, where the beginning and the end will be connected, so you will need to link the opening and closing ideas of the script.

If you have the opportunity, you can share the collective script on school notice boards, in local institutions or on social media.

Work proposals and methodologies for action

Take action

 We suggest that you organise a competition to design a poster, in groups, either by hand or using any digital design platform, highlighting women's struggle for free access to water.

Include a powerful image, a slogan related to some of the key concepts explored in the cases of the struggle for water, and a brief explanation of the conflict.

Display your posters on the school notice boards and set up a selection panel made up of teachers, students and families.

 Research an example in which women have been protagonists in water conflicts in Chile, Colombia, Argentina, Bolivia or any other country in Latin America.

Compare it briefly with the case of Lake Villarrica (Chile).

 Based on the information you have gathered, we suggest you produce content to upload to the Voces-Territorios App

You should adapt it to the five dimensions proposed: territorial processes, sociocultural processes, emotions, types of struggle, types of action.

To watch and read

Water in the documentary “La Cuenca” de Left Hand Rotation

<https://www.contested-territories.net/la-cuenca/>

The documentary approaches water from a relational and political perspective. Through multidimensional approaches, it integrates several key notions about water. Water, far from being simply a resource, is a vital element that sustains life and has a spiritual dimension. It is presented as a vehicle for emotional, cultural and symbolic connections, where everyday narratives converge in different sacred, natural and material dimensions. Water is also shown as a collective belonging, vital for all eco-dependent beings that make up the basin. The documentary articulates the idea of the basin not only as a hydrological unit, but as a geographical-political subject, where all tributaries and communities are "tributaries of the same body". It seeks to overcome the separation between the human and the non-human, proposing a political narrative based on the integration of all eco-dependent beings. The documentary uses water and the basin as a political bridge: it starts from the everyday to build the political. Water protection becomes a form of ecological struggle that highlights territorial conflicts, opposition to real estate or tourism projects, and the defence of ancestral territories. In short, "La Cuenca" revisits an ecological ethic that recognises the interdependence of all beings, with water as a central and articulating element.

On this basis, "La Cuenca" also shows the conflicts between different actors. The documentary clearly shows that these actors do not compete on equal terms, that the social, political, cultural, geographical and economic structures in which the different actors participate in tensions and conflicts already establish relations of inequality.

To watch and read

Water guardians and caretakers
A multi-voiced account of the struggles for water and life in Bolivia
Left Hand Rotation in collaboration with IIADI
<https://vimeo.com/1072988301>

Dawn in El Alto. The modernity of the latest communication infrastructure coexists with the outlines of a huge self-built city. Flows of people, streams of vehicles, traffic organised for greater efficiency, the struggle of time against space. Urban landscapes.

Water. Plastics, rivers that are life and, at the same time, dying in degraded landscapes. Water infrastructure that carries pollution. Rivers of colours. In these landscapes, as throughout the world, territories are undergoing acute processes of transformation in their productive matrix. The images come and go between the details and the landscapes that connect glaciers with channelled rivers entering and leaving the city, the communities, the fields. Left Hand Rotation, in collaboration with the IIADI (Institute for Research and Action for Integral Development), offers us four windows through which to observe the future of the guardians and caretakers of water.

1

UMA UÑJIRINAKA: Tiquipa and the struggles from below
Luis Flores Mendoza, Macario Gutiérrez Amaru, Victoria Lecoña Lecoña

The indigenous community of Tiquipa is located in the southern sector of the province of Los Andes. The camera focuses on situations in which the challenges of the present intertwine with the past and present of the Chiripa culture, an ancient pre-Inca civilisation historically located around Lake Titicaca.

We attend assemblies where traditional forms of organisation such as the Ayllú are articulated with minute books and bureaucratic forms. Lake Titicaca is present with its challenges and is also a place of remembrance and memory; these images are a record of the changes taking place in the lake and in the community, in the bodies that now feed on meat when they used to feed on fish.

El Alto and its uncontrolled growth. This municipality, together with Viacha, is closely linked to the pollution of Lake Titicaca; dirt, smell and disease that have been brought by the Pallina and Katari rivers for some time and then flow into Titicaca. The effects and consequences are diverse, profound and affect everyone. Weeds grow and spread, preventing access to water and grazing. Climate change brings harsher and longer droughts, reducing the water level of Lake Titicaca. Everything is changing.

The water guardians are active witnesses to a territory in transformation. They organise themselves into committees, clean drinking troughs and other water infrastructure, challenge municipalities and entities located along the basin, demand that they incorporate the environmental dimension into their territorial work, and think and imagine their territory and ways to make it possible. For these water guardians, the challenge is clear:
 "we have to rise up from below".

To watch and read

2

Puchucollo Alto and the guardians and caretakers of the "agüífero" (aquifer)

The Puchucollo community is located in the municipality of Laja, Los Andes Province, on the outskirts of the city of El Alto. The images show us daily life, crops, animals at the watering holes, and the anonymous daily work of sustaining life in the territory. We see houses nestled in hydrosocial territories crisscrossed by wetlands and rivers, under leaden skies. Schoolchildren and workers walk to school and to the fields, crossing landscapes of water and rubble, bridges and farms.

The rapid growth of El Alto is not possible without waste, excess and surplus. Although popular and baroque, El Alto is a large-scale destructive construction that produces houses, but also rubble. The enormous production of rubble does not disappear into thin air. Every day, mountains of rubble accumulate from trucks that dump these remains into the everyday landscapes of places like Puchucollo. These places seem destined to be sacrifice zones, the final destination of what is left over in other places. There, life is combined with landfills and other water problems: pollution and sewage from El Alto; tanneries, clandestine pipes, filtered water from the cemetery and decomposing bodies, a treatment plant that does not work and, at the same time, dry pipes with trickles of water, insufficient for everyday life. The camera takes us from these places to mud greenhouses, family homes, kitchens, and the hands that prepare food. In Puchucollo, the guardians and caretakers of the aquifer know who they are.

With small, everyday gestures, but also with organisation and struggle, they dream of a healthy and living aquifer for the whole community.

To watch and read

3

The Juancito Pinto educational unit and a territory between the sacred and the profane

Murals about water on a building constructed on a riverbed. Discourses on the territory of life in which it is located. The hollows as springs. The sacred and the profane around water. In the Andean world, the distinction between the sacred and the profane in relation to water is not a rigid separation, and water is simultaneously sacred and vital, natural and spiritual, forming part of a relational fabric in which humans, spirits and natural elements are deeply intertwined.

What from a Western perspective might be seen as "profane water" — everyday water, used for washing or irrigation — does not lose its quality in the Andean world. There is no sharp division between the sacred and the secular: the act of watering a field, for example, may be accompanied by small offerings or ritual words, recognising that this practical act also has a spiritual dimension.

Thus, stripping water of its sacredness has more to do with its degradation; with turning huacas into rubbish dumps, river basins into rubbish tips and living territories into a succession of 250 m² plots ready for building. The blood and entrails of animals from the slaughterhouse turn the Seque River into the backyard of some.

That same backyard is home to others.

For other geographies to be possible, it is necessary to imagine: planting trees, composting, collecting plastics, travelling.

Inviting students to imagine other territories with models, plans, narratives.

Educational actions around life for water and water for life.

To watch and read

4

Scale, memory and the construction of meaning for water conservation UMA UÑJIRINAKA: Upper Milluni

Climbing to the summits, to the glaciers, the silence, the cold, the white colour. The images follow the water in its permanent exercise of connecting. Herding sheep. We see a dam, as well as infrastructure that converts rich and sacred water into a resource.

Extracting without conserving.

The panoramic images remind us that millions of people are sustained in their daily lives by these waters that are invisible and apparently unrecorded; transported in pipes, they supply life in the city day after day.

This is not the only extraction in this place, as the documentary describes. In 1920, a British-owned mine was established in the territory. It extracted for years, then abandoned the site. Years later, former workers and their children returned and began work again. They do so, but on a different scale, the documentary emphasises. In these mountains, as in many other places along the entire Andes mountain range, mining has a long tradition. The extractivism we see today, with its destructive dynamics, is something else entirely, on a different scale and of a different nature.

24 May 1965. In a context in which miners were a force of opposition to the authoritarian government, dictator René Barrientos brutally attacked the camp. The exact figures are unknown; some sources speak of 60 people killed and dozens injured and detained. Like a city of low houses, the cemetery of the Milluni Mine stands there as a place of memory, historical and cultural heritage of El Alto, in the middle of a landscape of water that is also being fought to protect today.

The community tourism initiatives promoted by the Alto Milluni community today are part of this process. Resisting is not building. Food, clothing, dance and relationships are what matter; this is how these guardians of the water are fighting today to build meaning, territory and community in this place.

